

Dataset: Feedback on the Path2Integrity learning cards for research integrity (2020)

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Abstract

This dataset is drawn from feedback given by participants, lecturers, and experts on the Path2Integrity learning cards programme for research integrity in 2020. Positive as well as negative feedback is presented, thus recording what went well, what did not, and what must be improved. The data collected is viewed as crucial for the further development of tools for teaching and learning research integrity, in particular Path2Integrity's learning cards.

Keywords

Path2Integrity learning cards; research integrity; learning and teaching; development; feedback

Description of the dataset

This dataset lists feedback given in 2020 by various participants and educators on sessions using the Path2Integrity learning cards (Suppl. material 1). The Path2Integrity learning card programme (P2ILC) aims to build and enhance knowledge about reliable research and how to apply it. Participants “learn how to conduct a dialogue on the rejection or acceptance of norms in research integrity (Prieß-Buchheit et al. 2020). The programme's learning cards have been continuously used and developed since 2019 when they were

first published. (All learning cards and their different versions are available open access and published at [ZENODO.org](https://zenodo.org); for example, Lindemann and Prieß-Buchheit (2021)).

The feedback listed in the supplementary material contains reactions to the sessions both positive and negative and concludes the first dataset from 2019 (Häberlein and Claas 2020). The feedback comes from the participants themselves as well as from lecturers and experts reviewing the material. The feedback was given to the learning cards' (co-) authors by the educators who conducted the learning sessions. Although having different academic backgrounds, all trainers were familiar with the material and were thus able to share their differentiating insights on the successes and problems with the learning cards.

Each row of the dataset consists of several items, starting with the session number (first digit) and comment number (second digit), followed by the comment itself. The other columns provide information on the card version, the participants, the group size, as well as the year and country in which the session was conducted. The datasheet contains feedback regarding P2I sessions from four countries and international sessions. Some sessions are marked as online sessions and show that the feedback was collected in onsite as well as online sessions (Hermeking and Prieß-Buchheit 2021, in press).

The data collected was and is continuously used to improve the P2ILC. Although the learning cards were originally designed in English, some lessons were held in other languages, e.g. Spanish or German. Through this, linguistic recommendations were made which are used for translations as well as for how lessons are carried out in other European languages. The feedback supported the design of the second version of learning cards, the translation into several languages (e.g. German, Spanish, Danish, Polish), and the establishment of the P2I online learning environment (www.learning-p2i.eu).

P2I used the dataset for a constant development and refinement of the learning cards to ensure transparency and the inclusion of many perspectives.

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Grant title

Path2Integrity - Rotatory role-playing and role-models to enhance the research integrity culture

Hosting institution

Coburg University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Coburg, Germany

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Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Dataset

Authors: Ina Berg, Julia Prieß-Buchheit

Data type: Feedback

Brief description: Feedback on the Path2Integrity learning cards for research integrity (2020)

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